

DEVELOPING READING SKILLS BY DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract: Reading is undeniably important in learning the English Language especially to non-native speakers. With reading, it indirectly aids learners in acquiring other skills like, skimming, scanning, note-taking, vocabulary, and memory retention. It's good way for learner, if they improve their reading skills by digital technologies. We will try to explain it by this technology. Besides, through reading, a lot of knowledge and information can be gained to help learners in understanding the language.

Key words: reading skill, technology, digital technologies, retention.

РАЗВИТИЕ НАВЫКОВ ЧТЕНИЯ С ПОМОЩЬЮ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ

Аннотация: Чтение, несомненно, важно в изучении английского языка, особенно для тех, для кого он не является родным. Вместе с чтением оно косвенно помогает учащимся приобрести другие навыки, такие как беглый просмотр, сканирование, ведение заметок, словарный запас и сохранение памяти. Это хороший способ для более стройных людей, если они улучшат свои навыки чтения с помощью цифровых технологий. Мы попытаемся объяснить это с помощью этой технологии. Кроме того, посредством чтения можно получить много знаний и информации, которые помогут учащимся понять язык.

Ключевые слова: навык чтения, технология, цифровые технологии, запоминание.

INTRODUCTION

According to Anderson (1985) as cited by Amin (2019), reading is an important living skill, that ensures a child's success in school and even throughout his or her life. It is one of the important skills apart from Listening, Speaking and Writing. Being able to read can also secure good job in the future. A child's self-achievement and work accomplishment will almost definitely be wasted if he or she does not develop the habit of reading. (Amin, 2019). To become a successful reader, one must be able to identify words to comprehend individual sentences, as well as combine their meanings to provide an overall understanding of the text.

MAIN PART

Defining E-reading Technology in both popular media and research, terms such as e-book, e-reader, e-text, and tablet are not always clearly and consistently differentiated and are often used interchangeably. The lack of clarity in part reflects the rapid advance of technology, with newly released options almost immediately being modified or merged together with other options. Such change contributes to confusion as distinguishing features become vague or obsolete.

Innovative technology applications also show promise for supporting the development of advanced reading skills that students need to master discipline-specific knowledge areas and that may be particularly challenging for students from low socioeconomic backgrounds and non-English-speaking homes. Each child started a training program through the distance rehabilitation

platform Ridinet, using the Cloze app, after the assessment of learning and cognitive abilities, including comprehension assessment with two texts, one narrative and one informative (Cornoldi and Carretti, 2016; Cornoldi et al., 2017). Connection to the Ridinet web site was required in order to access to the app, three or four times a week for more or less 15/20 min. The period of use was of 3 months for 6 children and 4 months for 22 children. After this period children's comprehension was assessed again.

According to (Schiff & Calif, 2004) evaluating is considered as a post-reading strategy that reveals the needs of students to summarize the core ideas for comprehension of certain material and to find supplementary evidences for outside needs. In addition, Benchmark education (2011) informed that evaluating represents as a metacognitive process to judge the meaning of the text for using appropriately by fulfilling the needs of readers.

This strategy helps readers to make suitable conclusion of the text and make away to guess the meaning appropriately by planning for further reading strategies. Channa, Yossatorn and Yossiri (2012) investigated the attitudes of students towards activities used in classroom in Thailand. They found learners' perceptions and satisfactions on their teachers using class activities including teaching strategies, class activities and social environment.

CONCLUSION

This study investigated the effects of computer-assisted comprehension practice using a researcher-developed computer program, Computer-Assisted Collaborative Strategic Reading (CACSR), with students who had disabilities. In this study we compared the use of two supplemental balanced and strategic reading interventions that targeted the decoding, fluency, and reading comprehension of upper elementary and middle school students with reading disabilities (RD). All students had significant delays in decoding, fluency, comprehension, and language processing. Two comparable, intensive tutorial treatments differed only in the degree of explicitness of the comprehension strategy instruction.

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